

Synthesis of 2,3-Dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]pyrono[5,6-*f*]quinoline

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3-(2'-Hydroxyethyl)quinolin-2-(1*H*)-ones are the useful starting materials for the synthesis of furo-, thieno-, selenolo-, tellurolo- and 1*H*-pyrrolo[2,3-*b*]quinolines. Recently, we have reported¹ the chemical and photolytic one-step synthesis of 3-(2'-hydroxyethyl)quinolin-2(1*H*)-one (2) from *N*-aryl-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxanilide (1). The method involves the reaction of 1 with a Lewis acid like AlCl₃ and the other involves the photolysis of 1. Of the two methods, the photolytic method was established to be more productive¹. Several derivatives of anilide (1) have been synthesised and cyclised to corresponding quinolonylethanol (2)².

In continuation of our efforts to prepare and photolyse new *N*-aryl-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxani-

lides, we report here the preparation and photolysis of *N*-(6'-coumarinyl)-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxanilide (3) followed by the conversion of the resulting quinolonyl ethanol (4) to 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]pyrono[5,6-*f*]quinoline (5).

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Boetius microheating instrument and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectrum on a Hitachi R-600 spectrometer and mass spectra on a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer RMU-6E spectrometer (70 eV).

N-(6'-Coumarinyl)-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxanilide: A well cooled mixture of 6-aminocoumarin (0.1 mol) and pyridine (0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was stirred with simultaneous addition of 4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxylic acid chloride³ (0.1 mol) taken in dry benzene (50 ml). It was allowed to stand for 30 min and then poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from chloroform, (62%), m.p. 191–92° (Found : C, 64.9; H, 4.01; N, 5.3. C₁₄H₁₁O₄N requires : C, 65.37; H, 4.31; N, 5.44%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1100 (C–O–C), 1640 (C=C), 3250 cm⁻¹ (NHCO); δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.85 (2H, t, *J* 12 Hz, CH₂), 4.5 (2H, t, *J* 12 Hz, CH₂O), 6.5 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C_{3'}-H), 7.1–8.1 (5H, m, ArH. C_{2'}-H), 9.4, (1H, s, NH).

Photolysis of 3: A solution of 3 (500 mg) in dry methanol (300 ml) was purged with oxygen-free nitrogen for 15 min and then irradiated in a Rayonet 208 preparative photoreactor using

253.7 nm light for 25 h. The tlc analysis showed the absence of spot corresponding to the anilide. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl acetate-chloroform (1:1). The product was recrystallised from methanol, (225 mg, 45%), m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 65.3; H, 4.28; N, 5.35. C₁₄H₁₁O₄N requires : C, 65.37; H, 4.31; N : 5.44%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450 (OH), 1 640 (NHCO) and 1 710 cm⁻¹ (CO).

The spectral data thus showed that compound 3 has undergone photocyclisation, and the cyclisation is suggested to have occurred angularly with respect to 5,6-position of coumarin and not linearly with respect to 6,7-position. This suggestion is based on the non-equivalency of bonds called 'partial bond fixation' which is a common phenomenon in nearly all fused aromatic systems⁴. According to this, the C₅-C₆ bond will have higher double bond character rather than C₆-C₇ bond in coumarin. Thus the product was identified as 3-(2'-hydroxyethyl)pyrono[5,6-f]quinolin-2(1H)-one (4).

Cyclisation of 4 : To 4 (0.5 g) was added PPA (500 mg) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 4 h. It was then cooled and poured into ice-water and filtered. The clear filtrate was basified with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol, (250 mg, 53.8%), m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 69.71; H, 3.43; N, 5.7. C₁₄H₉O₃N requires : C, 70.29; H, 3.79; N, 5.85%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 720 (C=O), 1 645 (C=C) and 1 220 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). Mass spectrum showed M⁺ at m/z 239 (100%). The new compound thus synthesised was 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-b]pyrono[5,6-f]quinoline (5). The structure was further attested by a study on its mass spectral fragmentation pattern (rel. intensity %) : 240(28), 239(100), 238(24), 211(29), 210(12), 209(7), 184(5), 183(37), 182(20), 181(28), 180(6), 169(4), 168(3), 165(4), 164(3), 157(6), 156(10), 155(25), 154(45), 153(42), 152(11), 149(6), 127(6), 126(4), 125(3), 113(8),

112(4), 111(5), 99(10), 98(5), 97(8), 77(9), 76(6), 75(5), 63(13), 52(11), 51(31), 50(22), 43(13), 39(22), 38(9), 32(30), 28(60).

The most intense peak in the mass spectrum of 5 is the molecular ion peak itself. This compound shows fragmentation as expected for a coumarin^{5a}, dihydrofuran^{6a} and quinoline^{5b,6b} moieties. The initial loss of CO might be considered to have occurred from the coumarin moiety resulting in an ion 6 of m/z 211. Similar to dihydrofurans⁷ we may expect the subsequent expulsion of CH₂O, •CHO, and H• from the dihydro part of this ion and set basis for further fragmentations. Indeed the corresponding ions are observed at m/z 181, 182 and 210, which subsequently undergo elimination of HCN/CO/ CHO etc. forming various peaks at m/z values of 155, 154, 153, 152, 127, etc.

Similar to our observation in the mass spectra of furans^{5c}, we can propose the elimination of (CO + H•) and CHO• from the furan part of (M-CO) ion 6 leading to the ions at m/z 182 and 183 and these ions to decompose with the loss of CH₂O/C₂H₂ and CHO•/CH₂O respectively.

The fragmentation is also found to be initiated from the non-pyrone part⁸ of the molecular ion with the loss of H•, CHO• and CH₂O from M⁺ to give the daughter ions at m/z 238, 210 and 209 respectively. This is followed by the loss of HCN or CO and further fragmentations.

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NOTE

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